

Analysis of the Current Situation of the Players and Works of Guangdong Piano Music

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Abstract

This paper selects the piano players and works that have been introduced into Guangdong for more than 400 years as the research object, and analyzes the research situation from three aspects: the existing data and the content involved; the research perspective of the existing data; and the deficiencies and deficiencies in the current research. In the process of writing, the literature research method and content analysis method are adopted to classify and sort out the currently collected literature data, and analyze the literature content, and then that the research perspective of the existing data is mainly reflected in the following four aspects: growth experience; work research; historical records; and outstanding contributions. Through the research, it is beneficial to supplement the research content of the piano people and works of Guangdong piano music, To supplement the data on the development history of Chinese piano art, And for the majority of piano educators teaching Guangdong piano works to provide a systematic, comprehensive and detailed reference materials; It is helpful to let the experts and scholars studying Guangdong piano music have a comprehensive overview of the piano art in Guangdong in the development process, Summarize the gains and losses of the current research, the accumulated scientific methods, and rich experience, To promote the vigorous development of Guangdong piano art in the future; conducive to music lovers who are keen to learn Guangdong piano works, Provide assistance with the information, To further understand and get familiar with the piano players and works of Guangdong piano music, And will promote it, inherit and carry forward the vast number of people. Of course, only through the development of Chinese piano art over the past 400 years, can we better study the development of Guangdong piano music, to provide reference and help for the study of Guangdong piano music players and works. Today, the development of Guangdong piano art has accumulated fruitful results. Guangdong music and the piano works created by Guangdong composers are very important to the creation and development of Chinese piano works. It is they who created the history of the creation, performance history, and education history of Chinese piano music so that the art of piano can take root, sprout and grow in China.

Introduction

As the southernmost province of the Chinese mainland, Guangdong province has a superior geographical environment, beautiful wealth, and a developed economy. It has been one of the Windows of economic and cultural exchanges between the East and the West since ancient times. With the frequent economic exchanges between the East and the West, western culture in southern China first moved from Guangzhou and gradually spread to the whole country. As early as the Ming Dynasty, the western piano music culture was subsequently "imported", from the ancient piano to the modern piano, after more than 400 years of historical evolution. Today, Chinese piano art has attracted the world in both creation, performance, and education. Among them, in the process of early China piano art development, there are a large number of Guangdong composers, performers, and educators of Guangdong and even the national piano art development made outstanding contributions such as Chinese modern music education pioneer Ma Sicong, Mr. Chen Hong founded "Guangzhou music institute" (in December 1985, in memory of Guangdong people's musicians Xi' an, renamed "Qinghai music academy"), several school name, after several changes, bred Xi'an, xiao, me, li ling, a group of leading the trend of the modern Chinese music culture contact musicians. With the rich cultural resources, economic resources, and geographical advantages adjacent to Hong Kong and Macao, "Xinghai Conservatory of Music" has become an important base for training artistic talents in a strong cultural province in Guangdong, providing high-edge artistic talents with both integrity and ability for the whole country and even the world.

Throughout the 400 years of piano history, Guangdong includes piano composers, Xiao Youcheng, Lao Zhicheng, Huang Anlun, and Chen Yi, piano players Yang Jiaren, Bao Hui buckwheat, Li Qi, Du Ningwu, Chen Jie, piano educators Li Shuxin, Li Songwen, and 153 piano works created by Guangdong composers. Given the above achievements in the development of Guangdong piano art, some experts and scholars in the industry have studied the piano figures and works of Guangdong piano music from different aspects and concerns.

So, what is the research status quo of the piano people and works of Guangdong piano music? This is the main question to explore in this paper. Discussion on this problem: it is beneficial to supplement the research content of Guangdong piano music, To supplement the data on the development history of Chinese piano art, And for the majority of piano educators teaching Guangdong piano works to provide a systematic, comprehensive, and detailed reference materials; It is helpful to let the experts and scholars studying Guangdong piano music have a comprehensive overview of the piano art in Guangdong in the development process, Summarize the gains and losses of the current research, the accumulated scientific methods and rich experience, To promote the vigorous development of Guangdong piano art in the future; conducive to music lovers who are keen to learn Guangdong piano works, Provide assistance with the information, To further understand and get familiar with the piano players and works of Guangdong piano music, And will promote it, inherit and carry forward the vast number of people.

Based on the above research purposes, this paper selects the piano players and works who have been introduced to Guangdong for more than 400 years to analyze the research status of the piano players and works of piano music in Guangdong. Specifically from three aspects: first, the existing data (musicians, works, papers, etc.) and the content brief; second, the existing data (musicians, works, papers, etc.); third, the lack and deficiencies in the current research analysis.

II. Brief description of the existing information and the content involved

Through the collection of relevant materials of Research on Players and Works of Piano Music in Guangdong, the author divides it into three categories: (1) related research on Guangdong piano composers, performers, educators, and their piano works; (2) related research on composers who created piano works based on music in Guangdong materials; and (3) related research on Guangdong music. The existing information and the most representative information closely related to this article are summarized as follows:

(1) Research on Guangdong nationality piano composers, performers, educators, and related piano works created by them

1. Xiao Youmei (born in Xiangshan County, Guangzhou Prefecture, Guangdong Province, now Zhongshan City, Guangdong Province), the name Xiao Youmei, has searched for more than 180 articles. Among them, there are only two articles about the piano music "Night Song" and "New neon Dress feather Dance" created by Xiao Youmei. His piano song "Mourn Introduction" is rarely mentioned, let alone an analysis of the piano work. In 1925, the book Piano Textbook was published by the Commercial Press, which is a bibliography of Xiao Youmei's book on piano technical practice. The book is divided into three parts. The first is the basic exercises, the second is the primary technique, and the third is the famous music collection. The famous song selected in the third edition, contains a variety of expressions, playing methods, and choose of analysis, can arouse the interest of beginners in learning, and is of great help to beginners of composers.

2. Lao Zhicheng (from Shunde, Guangdong Province), like Xiao Yumei, belongs to the first generation of Chinese composers. With Lao Zhicheng as the name of the search net, a total of 21 articles, among which about his piano music "shepherd boy music" 3, "shepherd boy music" and Wang Jianzhong's "shepherd boy piccolo", and called the "shepherd boy" in the north and south, but few people know it. There are three other articles on piano music involved in the Title Piano Sketch. Lao Zhicheng's title piano works include "Autumn on the Grassland", "Preludes-Playing with Only the Left Hand", "Variations", "Sketch Collection", and "Xinjiang Rhapsody", these piano music research is rarely mentioned, it is a pity.

3. Ma Sicong (native of Haifeng, Shanwei, Guangdong province) is the first generation of Chinese violinist and composer. In addition to creating violin music, opera, ballet music, orchestra music, chorus music, and solo music, he has also created 7 piano works, including a piano concerto, piano sonata, piano solo music, piano quintet, etc. A total of 7 studies on Ma Sicong's piano works were searched by CNKI, with the largest publication volume in 2020. Among them, there is only one study on the Three Cantonese Songs written by Cantonese folk tunes. See Zhu Hao published in 2020, "A Brief Description of Ma Sicong <The Creative Characteristics and Enlightening significance of the Three Cantonese Songs>". This article explores the implication and pursuit of Chinese-style piano creation by analyzing the creative motivation of the three works. The author believes that this is in this period, as a Cantonese composer created an earlier Cantonese theme of piano works, we need to be more in-depth research and discussion.

4. Li Suying (a native of Nanhai, Guangdong Province) is the first generation of piano educator in China. After being engaged in piano education in Guangzhou in 1949, he devoted himself to the cause of piano education in Guangdong Province. As a veteran of the Guangdong music industry, he has taught many excellent players active in the Chinese piano industry, with students from all over the world. CNKI searched only 8

articles about Li Suxin, three of which were based on the interview record. For such a piano leader, literature is too lacking.

5. Rao Yuyan (a native of Dapu, Guangdong Province), and CNKI include only 11 papers related to piano works, one of which is a master's thesis. The —— takes the three pieces of <Chang'an ancient music polyphonic sketch> as an example. This paper takes the piano polyphonic works created by Rao Yuyan as the research object, starts from the structure and the creative characteristics of the music, analyzes the performance techniques of the three polyphonic works, and summarizes their artistic characteristics, which is a good example. Besides, Piano solos: "improvisation song first-hand car", "Introduction and fugue", "listen to the book to sing a harvest", "lyric poem" and other people mentioned, need to be further studied by future generations.

6. Chen Ligang (born in Haifeng, Guangdong Province), a piano educator. He learned the piano when he was a child and was admitted to Shanghai Music College during the Anti-Japanese War. CNKI searched a total of 8 articles, among which Liu wrote in 2013 "preaching on black and white keys —— visit piano educator Chen Ligang", the author in the form of interviews, professor Chen Ligang gave some constructive suggestions on the teaching of young teachers, children's piano test and piano practice methods.

Huang Anlun (born in Panyu, Guangdong province) is a prolific foreign composer who has composed 58 piano songs. CNKI retrieved 18 papers, including 12 master papers, all about the creation, performance, and style analysis of piano works, which can be referred to. The analysis of piano works such as "Prelineto in c-minor", "Four Fugue", and "The Little Match Girl" is rarely mentioned.

In short, according to the data collected at present, there are 30 Guangdong piano composers and educators, including 153 piano works, 9 of which were burned during the Cultural Revolution; 21 works with strong Lingnan style, including Ma Sicong, Three Cantonese Songs, Huang Rongzan, Lion Dance No.1 and Lion Dance No.2, etc. According to the data, we can see that the Cantonese music-style piano works created by Cantonese composers only account for 0.14% of the total number of works.

(2) Related research on composers who have created piano works based on Guangdong music materials

1. Chen Peixun, CNKI retrieved 109 articles on Chen's piano works in Guangdong, mainly focusing on five piano songs "Pinghu Autumn Moon", 16 articles on piano music "Double Flying Butterfly Theme Variations", 7 articles on piano music "selling groceries", 5 articles on piano music "Thinking Spring", and 8 articles on piano music "Dry Day Thunder". From the aesthetic point of view, artistic analysis, ethnic techniques, teaching, performance, and other aspects of the analysis and research, and other piano works analysis article is similar.

2. Wang Jianzhong, Wang Jianzhong's adaptation of the piano music, "Colorful Clouds Chasing the Moon", is one of the classical piano music adapted from traditional Guangdong music. CNKI searched a total of 45 articles, mostly including music analysis, performance skills, artistic performance, etc., and the research depth was relatively lacking.

Non-Cantonese composers create 29 piano works with Cantonese music style, such as 9 piano titles, including Xia Like; 5 piano titles, Thunder, Wang Day, Wang Jianzhong, 4 Piano Concerto, South China Sea, Cao Guangping, —— Nuwa with two Chaozhou gongs; Liu Shouyan, Liu Tianyi; Entertainment Ping, Fishing Song, Zhao Xiaosheng. Up to now, the detailed analysis and research of the above works are less involved, which need to be further supplemented by future generations.

(3) Related research on Guangdong Music

1. In 2009, Jin Lai's paper "Overview of the Development Road of Guangdong Piano Music (Upper, middle and Lower)" was serialized in Piano Art magazine. The three articles laid a strong foundation for the author's further study of Guangdong piano music. As an excellent piano teacher from Guangdong, the author introduces the development of piano in Guangzhou; the early piano education and performance; the contribution of foreign pianist Xia Like to the spread of Guangdong piano music culture; the restoration of Guangdong piano music development after the end of the Cultural Revolution in 1977; the contribution of the three major art schools in Guangdong Province, Xinghai Conservatory of Music, South China Normal University and Shenzhen Art School.

2. The book *Studies of Modern Guangdong Musicians*, written in 2012 by Feng Changchun and Li Minghui, has conducted a very detailed study of historical materials, demonstrated the artistic life and musical contributions of musicians from different perspectives, and provided detailed reference materials for the author to write this article. This paper introduces the historical contribution of Cantonese music master Lu Wencheng to the development of Guangdong music; collects the recent comments on musicians, artists, creators, the father of modern Chinese music, and the academic articles on Cantonese musicians such as Xiao Youmei, Chen Hong, and Cantonese musicians such as Ma Sicong, Xian Xinghai, He Anton, Li Ling, Liao Fu Shu, Zheng Zhisheng, and Ou Manalang.

3. Lu Qingwen, Lu Yinghua in 2013, the Oriental music —— Guangdong music, the article is based on Lingnan culture, tracing local three hundred years of traditional music culture, and the formation and development of Guangdong music, structure, melody, discussed in detail, but for the Guangdong piano history rarely mentioned, only introduces the piano since the early Ming dynasty in Guangdong time and place of Guangdong.

4. Tao Cheng's monograph "Guangdong Music" in Lingnan Culture ", written in 2018, studied" Guangdong Music ", which expressed opinions on the influence of foreign music culture, namely piano on Guangdong, and listed the representatives of Guangdong music and professional music groups established in Guangzhou one by one.

5. The paper, "Lecture Record of Professor Liang Maochun, —— of" Lingnan Style Piano Music ", was organized by Zheng Yunwei and serialized in three issues of Piano Art. The article is from Professor Liang Maochun's "Chinese Piano Works Seminar". This paper analyzes the concept and definition of "Lingnan style piano music", "the cultural characteristics of Lingnan music", "the development history of Lingnan style piano music", and provides a detailed material basis for the author to complete this paper.

6. Paper "Guangdong Folk Music in the Vision of Chinese Piano Music Culture" is the master's thesis of Liu Yan from Qufu Normal University. The article first introduces the application of early Cantonese folk music, the structure, form, content, melody, accompaniment instruments, and music style, and the development of Guangdong folk music, including the cultural charm, cultural connotation, development trajectory, national characteristics, aesthetic ability, national style, mutual integration, and expansion. The study of this paper deepens the regionality of piano creation in China.

7. "Discussion on the Style of Chinese Piano Works Adapted from Guangdong Music", the author Tan Xiangdong. The paper briefly discusses the concept of Guangdong music, and analyzes the style characteristics of his two Guangdong-style piano works, "Selling groceries" and "Si Spring", and the research depth is not enough.

8. Guo Dingchang, an author of "The Development of Lingnan Piano Music", explores the development of Lingnan piano music from the perspective of music aesthetics, and summarizes several characteristics of Lingnan style piano music, such as distinct local characteristics; the combination of Chinese and Western elements, and the nationalization of sound; the spiritual description of artistic conception, but the article is short and the content is not detailed.

9. Lv Shuxin, the author of The Five Piano Works Adapted from Guangdong Music, analyzes Chen Peixun's five piano works in Guangdong style, but the details of the structure, harmony, and tone are not explained in detail.

From the above data, it is mainly aimed at the development history of Guangdong piano music, the application of folk music, the style characteristics, individual works, and the description of individual musicians. The research on Guangdong piano music players and works is not comprehensive and profound enough, which requires further discussion by future researchers.

III. Analysis of the research perspective of the existing data

In the process of writing, this paper adopts the literature research method and the content analysis method, to classify and sort out the currently collected literature data, analyze the literature content, and then get the research perspective of the existing data.

Up to now, from the collected data, the research perspective of Guangdong piano musicians and their works is mainly reflected in the following four aspects: (1) growth experience; (2) works research; (3) historical records; (4) outstanding contributions.

3.1 Life experience

The study of piano music in Guangdong cannot study their family background, living conditions, growth environment, study process, economic status, etc., especially the process of music learning includes enlightenment, primary, intermediate to advanced teachers, which is a crucial aspect for every piano person. The collected data such as Feng Changchun, Li Minghui's 2012 works on the Studies of Modern Guangdong Musicians, Li Suying, Chen Ligang, and other musicians.

3.2 Work Study

From the found research data on Guangdong piano musicians and works, the research perspective is that most of the works study. Among them, 73 articles studied Chen Peixun's piano song "Pinghu Autumn Moon", 16 of "Double Flying Butterfly Theme variation", 7 of "Selling groceries", 5 of "Thinking of Spring", and 8 of "Dry Day Thunder"; Wang Jianzhong adaptation of the piano song "Colorful clouds chasing the moon" has 45 research articles; Xiao Youmei's piano music "Nocturne", "New neon Dress feather Dance" has two research articles; There are 3 research articles on the piano music created by Lao Zhicheng, and 3 research articles on the purpose of the piano music involved in the title of the piano sketch; Ma Sicong's piano works; Rao Yuyan has 11 articles on his piano works; There are 18 research articles on Huang's piano works. There are a few differences between the above works: some articles analyze and research from an aesthetic perspective, artistic analysis, ethnic techniques, teaching, and playing, some articles only focus on music analysis, playing skills, and artistic performance; some articles only study the technique of creation; some articles study the title characteristics of Guangdong piano music. and so on. From the perspective of work research, different research authors choose different angles and different concerns for the research of the same work and finally draw different conclusions, thus making the research of Guangdong piano works rich and colorful.

3.3 Historical records

Taking historical records as the research perspective is an essential source and foundation for the study of Guangdong piano music figures and works. For the vast majority of Guangdong piano musicians and works, the author obtains information through literature. Of course, there are also a few people obtained through interviews, which is the most skilled information. Guangdong piano music and works of study without the support of historical materials such as youmei xiao, Lao Zhicheng, Ma Sicong, Rao Yuyan, Huang Anlun musicians research, by Zheng Yun Wei finishing paper "Lingnan style piano music" —— professor Liang Maochun lecture record, theory, qing-wen lu, Lu Yinghua on the Oriental music —— Guangdong music, jin lai's paper "overview of Guangdong piano music development road (up, middle, down)", etc.

3.4 Prominent contribution

The piano music in Guangdong is all famous musicians in the music industry of Guangdong and even the whole country, with almost exception. Therefore, taking their respective outstanding contributions as the research perspective is in line with the research practice, and can also explain the problem, but also in their distinctive characteristics and shining points, which is worth in-depth study. The information has been found such as Xiao Youmei, Lao Zhicheng, Ma Sicong, Li Suxin, Huang Anlun, Chen Peixun, and Wang Jian medium musicians research.

IV. Analysis of the deletions and deficiencies in the current study

According to the currently collected data on the research of Guangdong piano music, although the academic circle has made many research achievements on the research of piano music in Guangdong, there are still some deficiencies and deficiencies and some areas to be further studied.

The research on Guangdong piano music piano people and works is scattered, the lack of overall research from the collected data research found that most of the individual musicians and works or musicians or work itself, few of the same period of Guangdong piano music piano people and work together, of course, the lack of overall research. To continue to develop the Guangdong piano art, it is necessary to do overall research.

There are few piano works in the Guangdong style, especially the early individual excellent works. Since the publication of China's first piano music in 1915, there are about 182 piano works created by Guangdong composers and non-Guangdong composers based on Guangdong music materials, but there are few that can be seen on the market at present." Pinghu Autumn Moon", "Colorful Clouds Chase the Moon", "Variations of the Double Flying Butterfly Theme", "Selling Grocery", "Dry Day Thunder" and other works are relatively rare. It is urgent for experts and scholars keen on Guangdong piano music and those studying their works to publish a collection of Guangdong piano works for the readers. Some musicians have been studied less, or even vacant.

At present, there are many researchers of Guangdong musicians such as Xiao Youmei, Chen Peixun, and Huang Anlun; fewer of Li Suxin, Ma Sicong, Rao Yuyan, Chen Weigang; and fewer of Chen Yi, Yang Jiaren, Li Qi, Du Ningwu, Chen Jie, Li Songwen and so on. The future needs to be committed to Guangdong piano music and work researchers to dig, organize and study.

There are relatively few piano people and works studying Guangdong piano music from the perspectives of music culture, characteristic local history, music image history, and aesthetics

The emergence of any art was influenced by the then environment, including cultural geography, cultural folklore, cultural exchange, diverse music culture, cultural morphology, and cultural comparison. The publication of Guangdong piano music players and their works is no exception, which is the nutrient and soil of the development of Guangdong piano art, namely: ecological environment. At present, the research is much the same, with the majority of the works themselves, and the research rising to a certain theoretical height is lacking. This requires studying Guangdong piano music from an interdisciplinary perspective.

Conclusion

In short, through the above of Guangdong piano music and works research status analysis, know, the piano process development regional research, must be attached to the process of global, music spread speed, make regional between mutual integration, mutual absorption, only throughout the development of Chinese piano art in more than 400 years, can better study the development of Guangdong piano music, for Guangdong piano music and work research to provide reference and help.

Today, the development of Guangdong piano art has accumulated fruitful results. As the Chinese piano specialization process rose, piano popularity, according to the collected literature, the author more think Guangdong music and Guangdong composer of piano works Chinese piano works creation and development are important, contributions have they created the Chinese piano music creation history, playing history, education, let the piano art to take root and sprout in China, development.

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